

Stability Constants of Complexes of Cu(II) and Be(II) with 2-Hydroxy 3-Methyl 5-Sulpho Benzoic Acid and 2-Hydroxy 3-Sulpho 5-Methyl Benzoic Acid

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THE electronic effects of the substituents on stability constants of metal complexes have been interpreted according to the current organic chemical theory. The groups capable of contributing electrons to the ring increase the complex stability whereas the groups attracting electrons decrease the complex stability. The substitution of methyl group, in general, should increase the stability constant whereas the substitution of sulphonic acid group should decrease the stability constant. An interesting case arises when both the groups are present in the ring and their positions are interchanged. With this in view, the stability constants of 2-hydroxy 3-methyl 5-sulpho benzoic acid (SoCA) and 2-hydroxy 3-sulpho 5-methyl benzoic acid (SpCA) with metal ions Cu(II) and Be(II) have been determined by pH-titration technique.

Experimental

The preparation of SoCA and SpCA has been described in our earlier papers^{1,2}. The stock solution of each ligand was prepared by dissolving a known amount of the substance in water followed by standardization of the solution by the usual procedure. The solutions of copper(II) and Be(II) ions were prepared by dissolving a known amount of their sulphates in water. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution was prepared from a concentrated solution of sodium hydroxide appropriately diluted with freshly boiled and cooled distilled water.

For determination of stability constants Calvin and Wilson's³ extension of Bjerrum's method as adopted by Singh and Banks⁴ was used. Two titrations were performed in each system. In the first case ligand in 0.1M NaClO₄ was titrated against sodium hydroxide and in the second case the ligand + metal ion (1/5 of ligand concentration) in 0.1M NaClO₄ was titrated against the same sodium hydroxide solution. The initial total volume of solutions was 100 ml in both the cases.

The quantity \bar{n} , the average number of ligands bound per metal ion, was calculated from the

difference of the two titration curves⁴. The free ligand concentration was then calculated from the relationship

$$[L] = \frac{L^0 - \bar{n}M^0}{\phi}$$

where $\phi = 1 + [H]/K_{c_1} + [H]^2/K_{c_1}K_{c_2}$ and K_{c_1} and K_{c_2} are the carboxyl and phenolic dissociation constants (concentration quotients) respectively. The values of K_{c_1} and K_{c_2} were calculated from the apparent dissociation constants reported earlier². Knowing \bar{n} and $[L]$, the stability constant values were calculated from usual methods⁵ (Table 1). In another set of experiment the ligand to metal ratio was kept 10, but it did not alter the log k values.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES
I=0.1 (NaClO₄), Temp. 25°±1°

Ligand	Method	Cu(II)		Be(II)	
		log k_1	log k_2	log k_1	log k_2
SoCA ($pK_{c_1}=2.54$)	1	9.74	6.70	12.12	8.96
	2	9.72	6.73	—	—
SpCA ($pK_{c_1}=2.52$)	1	10.70	6.90	12.54	9.06
	2	—	—	—	—
(pK _{c₂} =13.47)	3	10.71	7.03	—	9.08

1. From formation curve

2. From the equation $\frac{\bar{n}}{(1-\bar{n})[L]} = k_1 + \frac{2-\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}}k_1k_2[L]$

3. From linear plot of

$$\log \frac{1-\bar{n}}{\bar{n}} \text{ vs } pL \text{ (for } 1.0 > \bar{n} > 0.0),$$

$$\log \frac{2-\bar{n}}{\bar{n}-1} \text{ vs } pL \text{ (for } 2.0 > \bar{n} > 1.0).$$

All experiments were carried out at room temperature maintained at 25°±1° and ionic strength of 0.1 (NaClO₄).

Discussion

It is clear from Table 1 that the substitution of methyl and sulphonic acid groups has marked influence on phenolic group and has little effect on carboxyl group. Hence the groups capable of contributing electrons to the ring increase the basicity of the phenolic group and thus increase complex stability, whereas the groups that attract electrons decrease the phenolic basicity and complex stability as well. As the presence of substituent on *ortho* or *para* position transmits the electrical effect to the reaction centre to the same extent, it is expected that the net effect will be the same irrespective of whether the methyl or the sulphonic acid group is *ortho* or *para* to the phenolic group and hence the stability constant value should not change when their positions are interchanged. On contrary to this the value of the 1:1 complex changes. It appears that in addition to the polar effect some other effect is playing an important role. The pK_{c_1} value of SpCA is greater than SoCA and this has been attributed to the additional hydrogen bonding in

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SpCA². As the dissociation of phenolic group decreases, it is natural that complex stability increases. It may further be noted that the interchange of position has little effect on log k_a value.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Ruthenium(III) Chloride Catalysed Oxidation of Benzyl Alcohol by Hexacyanoferrate(III) Ion in Aqueous Alkaline Medium

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KINETICS of the oxidation of alcohols via catalysed or uncatalysed route are reported in much details. However, the ruthenium(III) chloride catalysed oxidation of benzyl alcohol by hexacyanoferrate(III) ion has not yet been studied. In the present study we have carried out the ruthenium(III) chloride catalysed oxidation of benzyl alcohol by hexacyanoferrate(III) ion in aqueous alkaline medium.

Experimental

The potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) was G. R. (S. Merck) grade and NaOH was BDH, AR grade. The solution of ruthenium(III) chloride was prepared by dissolving the sample in very dilute hydrochloric acid. The final strengths of HCl and RuCl₃ were kept at 16.38 × 10⁻² and 4.76 × 10⁻² M respectively. The sample of benzyl alcohol was BDH, AR grade and solution was prepared by weighing. The progress of reaction was followed by estimating the hexacyanoferrate(III) at different intervals of time. In all the kinetic runs the alcohol was kept in excess.

Results and Discussion

The reaction velocity follows zero order kinetics with respect to hexacyanoferrate(III) ion concentration. The oxidation rate which follows nearly first order kinetics with respect to lower concentration of the alcohols tends to zero order at higher concentration. Reaction rate goes on decreasing with

increasing hydroxide ion concentration. Reaction rate is directly proportional to the ruthenium(III) chloride concentration. A plot of 1/Rate vs [OH⁻] gives a straight line showing inverse proportionality of the rate with respect to hydroxide ion concentration. So, on the basis of aforesaid results, at lower alcohol concentration the reaction rate may be written as

$$-\frac{d[FeY]}{dt} = \frac{k[Ru(III)]_T[S]}{[OH^-]} \quad \dots (1)$$

where [FeY] represents [Fe(CN)₆]³⁻, [S] represents the alcohol concentration and k is a rate constant.

Reacting species of ruthenium(III) chloride in aqueous alkaline medium : Electronic spectral studies have confirmed that the ruthenium(III) chloride exists in the hydrated form¹ as [Ru(H₂O)₆]³⁺. Metal ions of the form [Ru(H₂O)₆]³⁺ are also known to exist as [Ru(H₂O)₅(OH)]²⁺ in alkaline medium^{2a}. In the present study it is quite probable that the species [Ru(H₂O)₅(OH)]²⁺ exists as [Ru(III)(OH)_x]^{3-x}. The value of x would always be less than six because there is no definite report of any hexahydroxy species^{2a} of ruthenium. The remainder of the coordination sphere will be filled by water molecule. Thus, all the ruthenium(III) chloride existing in the above form in aqueous alkaline medium will be the actual reacting species. It has been observed that the transition metal complexes are good abstracting agents for the hydride ion^{3,4}. The abstraction of α-hydrogen in acidic medium from 2-propanol has also been observed⁵. In a similar manner, Chatt *et al*⁶ concluded from their studies that the hydride ion transfer takes place from the α-carbon atoms of alcohol molecule or alkoxide ion. Therefore, one can safely conclude the abstraction of hydride ion from the alcohol molecule by ruthenium(III) in the present case also.

On the basis of the above the following scheme of oxidation is proposed.

The coordinated water molecule has been omitted for the sake of simplicity.

Considering the equilibrium condition for the complex formed in step I and knowing that

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